

Tourists of the future: importance of pro-environmental attitude among secondary school children

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Abstract - In the last few years the importance of responsible thinking, ethic and the sensitivity to the environment have become a significant part of the postmodern tourism. The people in the service sector, the agents, the ministers and other decision-makers and the travellers are more and more conscious about the questions of social and environmental effects. The members of the new generation, who are the young, against the elder people have a tendency to travel, have much more information about the technical details of the journey and how to organize it. The following questions can arise: whether the secondary school students know the effects of their travels; whether they know that their visits can have a positive or negative influence on the environment or the society of the destination. The first purpose is to acquire more information about the topic, since if we know the deficiency and faults of the education, the alteration of it can happen easily. The study shows the secondary school students' the sensitivity to the environment, reports the narrow cross sections, where the people who are in connection with the students (for example teachers, parents, older acquaintances) can help in creating an ethic and conscious aspect.

Keywords - responsible education, ethical tourism, education, sustainable, environmental awareness

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Introduction

The idea of the present study and research took a long time to mature developing gradually until it reached its current state. The background of undergraduates is heterogeneous. Students with radically different upbringing and social status both from the capital city and from the most disadvantaged villages attend the same educational institution. The curriculum of the tourism-hospitality major heavily relies on the subjects taught at secondary schools such as geography, history, mathematics, etc. Owing to these differing levels of background knowledge it is a great challenge to complete the requirements and to teach at the expected high standards. (General Educational Development Strategy, 2014-2020) As a matter of fact specialized subjects are more favoured by vocational school students while science subjects are more easily attainable for grammar school students.

The social and environmental sensitivity, knowledge beyond the curriculum, interdependency and the understanding of the relationships cannot be associated with school type. Basic concepts related to sustainability, environmental-, health- and ethical issues reflect the individual student's interest and the composition of the micro community the student is in. Heterogeneity in this case is even more prominent than in the case of the obligatory knowledge. All this means that teaching about sustainable tourism, describing the adverse impacts of tourism or explaining the directions of modern nutrition is much more complex task. The

different background, of course, determines the susceptibility of these objects.

The question arises, however, whether it is too late to talk about sustainability and the pollution of our environment for the first time to 20-year-old college students in the digital era when every young person is aware of and use the Internet and share information. If we are to understand the cause of the problem it is not college students but the 14-19 year olds that must be taken a closer look at.

This research does not aim to analyse the mandatory teaching materials or to reveal their shortcomings in sustainability, rather the goal is to show a general view of the attitudes of the age group in question towards the environment, healthy lifestyle and ethical behaviour. Another objective is to point out the weakest point of the age group concerning sustainability since the strengthening of this could help the next generation of professionals – and tourists – to become adults who behave responsibly towards the environment and society.

Sustainability in education – literature review

Sustainability and sustainable development is a guiding principle that permeates every scene of the economy, in the optimal case they are the determining factor of all processes and activities. Following the first appearance of the concept in 1987 it has become by now well-known and used in almost every walk of life. Education plays a very important role, from

kindergarten to university, in raising extensive awareness and presenting the concept in a comprehensible form to all sectors of society. Awareness and environmental consciousness have been a top priority in recent decades in the European Union and with that in Hungary as well. The pedagogical practice and the curriculum had to be restructured, sustainability has been incorporated into the laws, regulations and directives, and thereby this is now a properly researched, amply supported area of the science of education.

The Constitution of Hungary (25 April, 2011) emphasizes the protection of natural resources and it calls to take steps towards sustainable development. In addition to natural values it supports the sustainability, the importance and continuity of culture which it connects to education and learning. Thus part of the responsibility for disseminating knowledge on sustainability is placed into the hands of educational institutions. On 20 December 2002 the 57th General Assembly of the United Nations declared the period between 2005 and 2014 the Decade of Education for Sustainability. The UNESCO document "Education for sustainability" drafted in 2002 calls for a complete change in attitude in education and makes interdisciplinary approach, future-oriented vision, and lifelong learning as a strategic objective. (Education for Sustainability, UNESCO 2002)

Education in Hungary witnessed the appearance of a number of milestones – joining to the Copernicus Network, the appearance of Green Schools/Eco-Schools, degree programs and subjects related to nature- and environment protection at all levels of education - underpinning the legitimacy of the idea. (Czippan 2003) The program fits the UN Millennium goals of the Education For All Program, and numerous other international organizations, governments, civil society groups have joined in, making its complexity and importance apparent. The simultaneous application of the horizontal and vertical approach requires cooperation among disciplines on the one hand and the interoperability, continuity and consistency of the different educational levels on the other. In 2010 the Council of the European Union asked the member governments to do this. (Eur-Lex 2010) The priority axes were as follows:

- building "Lifelong Learning" programs in the national strategy,
- inclusion of the background knowledge of sustainable development in the curricula,
- interdisciplinary approach from kindergarten to university,
- elimination of financial problems,
- further training of educators, teachers, pedagogues, strengthening attitudes to sustainability,
- involvement of local communities and non-governmental organizations, strengthening cooperation

of institutions and the participants of different profiles, developing international relations.

The principle of sustainability is of course decisive in other areas especially if the whole industry is dependent on the preservation of natural and cultural values. These include tourism, where the importance of sustainability has been emphasized for decades by researchers and stakeholders. Today, the survival of several attractions is at stake, which can be realized determinedly only by means of sustainable tools. (Inskeep 2000) This requires professionals who are aware of the principles of sustainability, the proper direction of development and are also committed.

In the National Sustainable Development Strategy Hungary's Government emphasized that the education must have an awareness raising effect in the achievement of long-term sustainability, which will result in a responsibly producing and consuming society. (National Sustainable Development Strategy 2007) This also includes those who decide to enjoy a holiday trip, the tourists. The negative perception of the behaviour of Hungarian travellers - both at domestic and international level – could greatly be improved if schoolchildren become familiar with an ethical and environmentally conscious lifestyle as well as with sustainability from the very beginning. Focusing on the above mentioned problems the authors attempted to carry out a pilot study on the borderline of education and sustainability - ethical tourism – whose results will outline the direction of further studies and that could exactly point out the deficiencies of the behaviour and thinking of future tourists. These deficiencies, which can be corrected by tourism experts after graduation while being involved in tourism development, can have significant influence.

Research methods and demography

Full-time students of the Szechenyi Istvan Roman Catholic High School in Hatvan were selected to participate in the survey. The reason for this is that the school is situated in a small town that does not belong to the agglomeration of the capital city, but it is not far from it either. Employment and earnings are around the national average (Central Statistical Office) therefore it is able to represent the secondary schools free from extremism. The school district of Hatvan includes 14 secondary schools of which three – including the one the research focussed on – are church-run. (Public education development plan, Heves County 2013-2018.) Accordingly, religious education is stronger than in conventional public or private institutions, which may influence or change the students' attitudes towards ethical behaviour.

The samples includes a total of 262 people, which is 76.3% of the students attending 9-12 grades plus seven other students of grade 14 of vocational training. On

this basis, the respondents were 17-18 years old at the time of sampling (Fig.1.), which occurred in spring 2014. 50.8% of the respondents were women and 49.2% men. The questionnaires, filled out at discussion class with the form master, were later digitalised to ease processing. The survey included two questionnaires: a longer one containing 43 different types of questions attempted to provide an objective picture of the students' lifestyles and attitudes regarding sustainability; the second one had 24 prompt questions focusing on the environment, modern consumption and extracurricular knowledge about everyday topics. The results were processed in the Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet, the correlation study focussed on topics chosen subjectively by the authors.

Figure 1. Distribution of respondents according to the year of birth

Of the questions on demography the type of dwelling and its distance from the school were decisive since these early experiences in transport – especially public transport – may determine how the prospective tourists will travel and their attitude towards alternative and environmentally friendly means of transport. (Jaszberenyi 2008) Based on the responses related to the type and size of the residential settlement it can be stated that 40% of the respondents live in Hatvan, two people live in Budapest while the others are from the catchment areas of the city.

The composition of the family showed a similar picture as the Hungarian average (Central Statistical Office), around 20% of the children were being brought up by parent, while the other lived with their natural or foster parents. 25.2% of the student lived in a one-child family or the sibling lived elsewhere and the other respondents lived together with their – mainly only one

– siblings. 224 people (85%) had their own rooms where they can learn safely. Most of the respondents (62%) classified their families average in respect of living standards, 8.4% lived more modestly than the average, but 27.9% indicated that their living standard was slightly higher than the average and 1.5% noted that they had very high living standards.

Results

Transportation

The position of a settlement (Figure 2) has an impact on public transportation from many aspects as, first of all, the proximity of the M3 motorway makes the life of those living on the axis of Budapest-Gyongyos easier but its proximity to three counties can cause a problem for different bus companies. All the students commute to school on a daily basis and none of them stay in the student hostel. Sixty nine percent live in Heves, 26% in Pest, 3% in Jasz-Nagykun-Szolnok and 2% in Nograd county.

Figure 2. The position of Hatvan
 Source: authors' own compilation on the basis of http://hu.wikipedia.org/wiki/Magyarorsz%C3%A1g_megy%C3%A9i

Twelve students live farther than 30 km from school and 131 live between 10 and 30 m, 119 even closer and 20 persons live within less than 1 km. On the average, it amounts to 11.2 km in the sample. The city of Hatvan is divided by two prominent parts: the school is situated on the west side, the so-called New Hatvan part where the railway station (green arrowhead) and the central bus station (purple arrowhead) is quite a long way away, 1-1.5 km (Fig. 3.). They can be accessed only by taking a big detour due to a wrongly constructed intersection or by taking local buses.

The most frequently used means of transport are coaches (47.7%), local buses (14.9%) followed by cars (8%) and only 5.3% of the students take the trains. Twenty-one % walk to school and 2.7% ride a bicycle. The most preferred alternative following the most frequently used mode is the personal car (55.7%) so obviously, the students have to use public transportation but if there is a chance, they prefer cars.

Only 1% of the families concerned do not have a car. Bicycles as the alternative means of transportation were opted for by 21 students (0.08%), which reflect the present-day young's weak connection to sports and a healthy way of life. Although there would be opportunities as 85.2% of the examined students have a bicycle. The frequency and purpose of using them also were subject to analysis. Most of them use the bicycle occasionally and 17% said they used them very rarely or never. They see bicycles as a functional instrument that help travelling within the settlement or doing some minor business. One-third of the users regard bicycles as instruments for doing sports or a pleasant way of spending free-time. Only 5 students marked it as a hobby: 4 BMX fans and a mountain biker.

Figure 3. Location of the school

Source: authors' own compilation on the basis of <https://www.google.hu/maps/@47.7871482,19.9389902,15z?hl=hu>

Evaluations in connection with public transportation showed a very varied picture as 52 students were satisfied and never complained. Most negative opinions are rather connected to a concrete case such as the timetables do not match the timing of lessons at school, buses are rarely run and only 39 complained about the quality of the vehicles.

Waste management

Waste management and the attitude of the young to this topic are a priority regarding sustainability. The question whether was possible to collect waste separately was answered by 'yes', 'no' and 'do not know' by one-third-one-third, respectively although 20 m from the school building there is an isle and a selective container on the yard. The traditional mixed litter bins can only be found in the classrooms and corridors. Based on the answers the families of the students take good care of waste management as 16.1% select waste totally, 60.2% partially and the rest does not do it at all. However, selection can refer to separating food and materials to be burnt as mostly they live in houses with a garden so the proportion of 23.8% not selecting is quite high. It is especially discouraging knowing the fact that nearly one-quarter of the students (22.5%) have a selective trash isle within 400 m from home and another 25.1% within

maximum 1.5 km. The question how the generation between 14 and 20 could be encouraged to select was answered by only 160 students - 37 stating that it was not possible. This is a shocking ratio which is exceeded by the power and importance of advertisements, videos and the media. Some regard campaign and competitions as a solution while others believe in setting examples and 32 students wanted to have some reward or money (19) for selection. Only five of them stated that fines and punishment are proper deterrents. Apathy, abandonment and disappointment in their own generation are reflected in the answers with the strange fact that although their generation was addressed, none of the respondents identified themselves with the ones in the questions so all of them said 'they cannot be encouraged or it should be done' instead of I or we. It shows that students see themselves differently from the others and were not identified with these problems and solutions.

Another open question wanted to find out if the respondents knew how municipal waste in the household could be reduced. One hundred and seventy students answered but 22 'did not know' and 30 did not understand the question and answered that 'trucks should come more frequently' or 'slimming diet', 'saving' or 'bins should be placed more frequently'. Of the relevant responses we can mention conscious buying habits and meals (textile shopping bags, avoiding buying useless things or giving them away, looking for minimal wrapping, shopping on the market etc.) and recycling. Incineration and composting were also mentioned but on the whole, the result is not promising as the ratio of those who were unable to interpret this question was quite high. Recycling itself could be a good idea but we can suppose the content of this fashionable term is not entirely known by students.

Meals

The eating habits and attitude of the tourists of the future to food can affect what importance they give to the gastronomy of a destination, how they value authentic flavours and appreciate food (Kovacs 2012). In the examined secondary school the students' preferences and the supplies of the buffet were analysed. Twenty-five % of students have breakfast as the most important meal by many at home and most of them (56.2%) have ready-made or home prepared sandwiches or bakery products. Six percent buy something from the buffet for breakfast and, unfortunately, nearly 10% have no breakfast at all. Lunch was a special issue as there is no canteen at school so half of the students have cold cuts or sandwiches, one-quarter chooses the buffet and another quarter have no lunch at school only later, presumably at home. Accordingly, the buffet has bakery products and sandwiches on offer together with unhealthy fast food (pizza, hamburger, gyros). The most popular food is sandwich and bakery products, the next category,

pizza and hamburger, are only half as popular. Hot sandwich, sweets, chocolate, gyros and fornetti are the least popular. Unfortunately, all the sandwiches are made from white rolls and there are no vegetarian options. There are only minimal vegetables in the food and bakery products mostly mean products for sugar and white flour. The picture is gloomier regarding drinks as 45% of all the responses were only one product, Coca-Cola. Mineral water amounted to 14%, tea (both ice and hot) 12%, mush ice 10% and fruit juices only 7%. There were no energy drinks and coffee was not too popular with students, either (2.8%). Obviously, cola is not popular because of its caffeine content. The students also assessed the offered food of the buffet from 1 to 5 ranging from very unhealthy (1) to very healthy (5). The result is 2.72, which reflects that the young feel what they drink and eat is not healthy and they have enough information to decide but they are not willing to change. During the interview with the operator of the buffet it became obvious if he tries to come up with some healthy new products, there is no demand for them. He knows a lot depends on him and he is partly responsible for the students' health but he emphasises that the market rules and profit can only be realised by trendy food and drinks. He assessed the buffet's healthy food and drink supply to 4 emphasising that there is onion in the hamburger,

cucumber in the sandwiches and chicken in the gyros which are healthy.

Most of the students in Hatvan (59.6%) said they only had fast food once or twice a month although 3.1% on a daily basis in spite of the fact that there is not a single unit of any multinational restaurant chains in the city. This ratio is much worse in the capital (Fulop-Szakaly 2007). The examined group was very well informed in connection with meals, which is supported by their answers to the final question. They were asked what they would change if they could decide to eat healthily. There were 214 responses although the number of the items is much higher as many of them listed several dishes. It is interesting that only eating was stressed but 21 also mentioned doing sports. Table 1 presents the answers in three groups. The number of mentioning is after the factors to be changed.

The Table clearly presents that those concerned do not know what they should and should not consume but probably the reasons are known. Education should spend more time on the global food industry trends, changing the ingredients and the effects of the chemicals so that students could see this problem as a whole.

Table 1. Alternatives for changing the diet

Less	More	No change
1. fast food (hamburger, hot dog, pizza) – 36	1. fruit – 76	
2. chocolate, sweets, cookies – 29	2. vegetable – 72	
3. fizzy drinks, cola – 26	3. more liquids, mineral water – 20	
4. fatty, oily dishes – 22	4. white meat, chicken – 13	
5. carbohydrate, sugar – 20	5. salad – 9	1. Those who already live healthily and need no change belong to the first category – 17.
6. bread, white flour – 8	6. fewer meals or less portions more frequently – 9	
7. chips, craving – 6	7. regularity in eating – 7	
8. bakery – 4	8. cooked meals – 6	
9. salt – 4	9. no food in the evening – 5	2. The second category is for those who are not willing to 'chew any green' with a negative comment (12).
10. additives, preservatives – 3	10. natural/organic food – 3	
11. spices – 3	11. variety – 2	
12. cigarette – 3	12. a lot of protein – 2	
13. sweetener – 2	13. wholegrain bread/bakery – 2	
14. meat – 2	14. vegetable sauce – 2	
15. pasta – 2	15. mentioned once: fish, broccoli, oat, muesli, rice, sugar-free refreshments, paleolite diet	
16. mentioned once: potato, sandwich, pork, energy drink, refined cereals, food containing E, alcohol		

Source: authors' compilation

Education, environmental knowledge

Mapping the knowledge of the students on sustainability was only possible by surveying their education.

The thorough knowledge of sustainability is essential so that the ecological systems could be managed as a whole by society in the future and the points of tackling the harmful effects could also be detected (Kerekes 2013).

The survey examined this from two aspects: by questions on education and by checking their knowledge. Although the school is prominent in economics and IT, the dominance of either arts or sciences could not be felt. It is reflected by the list of the favourite subjects as without the leading one, P.E., the further order is English, literature, maths, history and IT. The quality of education was also assessed which reflects that they are aware that they have to learn a lot but many would require extracurricular activities. Half of the students are satisfied with the lessons, think that the subject is useful and 75% evaluate the teachers to be kind and well-prepared so we can say that the standard of education is quite high. Turnover is very low at the institution and a stable staff of teachers can deal with the students. Having a religious managerial board, we can ask how catholic principles and moral issues can be integrated into education and students' lives. Observing religious holidays, masses and religion classes must have an impact even in today's world. It is interesting that 60% of the respondents do not think the religious nature of the school is an advantage and cannot feel its positive impacts (due to resources, technical development is of higher level, more programmes charity etc.) What is more shocking is that although the Bible teaches modesty, self-sacrifice, kindness and taking care, 72.2% of the students stated that the hypothesis according to which catholic principles and environmental protection are closely related is false. This justifies Toth's statement (2009) that proves that sustainable societies and religious communities are not identical although they are based on similar moral issues.

In the near future the board of the school is trying to meet the requirements of an eco-school and be run on the principles of sustainability. However, this effort cannot reach the students as the answers were quite strange to the question asking about the differences of education in an eco-school. Of the 173 responses only 106 felt that they could obtain knowledge on environment protection in an eco-school while 41 have never heard about it and 18 thought that waste selection was taught and saving, healthy eating, old traditions and agriculture were also mentioned.

In connection with examining sustainability the questionnaire contained several concrete questions on the topic. An average of 3.29 was the result of the question how well-informed the students thought they were on the environment on a scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (absolutely). Half of the students gave 3 but there were 6 who gave themselves 1 and 15 students who felt they were entirely well-informed. Afterwards, the sources of this knowledge had to be evaluated, i.e. 9 factors on a scale from 1 to 5. The most obvious result were gained in the case of the 'impact of the Church' as 52% of the students gave it a 1. A similarly weak result can be noticed in the case of 'an impact of one of my teachers' although breakdown is more refined than

the previous one. This is quite discouraging for the teachers as it would (also) be their task to base knowledge on the environment and arouse interest. In addition, 'inner drive' as the motivating force of gaining knowledge proved to be much stronger and reached an average of 3.

Comparing elementary schools with secondary ones, the previous ones have had a more intense impact on the students with a minimal difference when it comes to the environment. Media and the internet also had an outstanding place as most students assigned a high number to them. This fully justifies the research of Asunta (2004) who concluded the same in connection with the Finnish and German secondary school students and proved that most sources of information on environment protection derive from the media. Moreover, it also turned out that friends (peers) have fewer effects from this aspect than the family, parents and siblings. The respondents also had the opportunity to test their knowledge and list the most severe environmental problems. Two hundred and eighteen responses arrived with sometimes long lists, so Table 2 also presents the number of cases in brackets.

The Table shows what the timeliest topics are in the press and also if the students really have knowledge on these topics and they really care. But can they see the possible treatments and cures of these problems? Different alternatives had to be assessed how much they could contribute to the future of the Earth. According to the results students do not obviously trust in the work of the state and the effectiveness of taxes but they could find the factors that could not really help. They have less faith in green organisations although selective waste collection is regarded to be a solution by many maybe because it has frequently been mentioned. At the last statement 'buy and consume less, live more modest' only some of them felt the relationship between environmental damages and the structure of consumption. Previously, when listing problems (Table 2) 12 students mentioned overproduction and 72 'a more responsible shopping' when talking about the ways of reducing waste in the household. Using a car is not regarded a serious problem (and public transport as a solution) so answers are evenly distributed. Interestingly, they can hardly feel the difference between markets and supermarkets so they do not consider it as a good solution based on the responses although there are lots of things that support the markets ranging from wrapping (overwrapping) to local produce and producer as well as harmful emissions of transportation. The statement about meat consumption also had shocking results as 90% of the respondents thought that keeping animals for slaughter and consuming them had no negative effects on the environment. Using energy saving bulbs was also considered to be partly good and reducing wasting of water (e.g. having a shower instead of bathing) did not mean a solution for the respondents.

Examining the consuming habits of the students was focused on the desired instruments and objects. At the time of the survey 87% of the students had a smartphone while the others had a traditional one. Only one of them did not have a phone and 95% had a Facebook profile that could be followed on 604 own electronic devices (laptop, smartphone, tablet and desktop) by 262 students. Thirty-two percent also had a video camera and 42 owned a scooter, motorbike or a car. Based on the statements above it can be concluded that the ratio of luxury products was quite high in the generation without income. The effect of the consumer society is that most teenagers had a definite idea what else they could need or have in addition. Miles (2003) stated that the consumption of the young is the basis of their communication in real as they can earn the respect of the community this way represented by their clothes, appearance, entertainment and the possessed IT devices. It was concluded on the basis of the open question where they were asked to write what they would do if they got 100.000 Ft and could buy everything on it Twelve did not give a concrete answer, two replied they owned everything they needed. The other objects or ideas were grouped into two

categories: useful and useless. The latter one consisted of 202 while the previous had 118 items. Fashionable clothes and shoes were the first by 63 replies followed by phones, cars or motorbikes with 10-15 mentioning as well as sweets jewellery, driving license and parties (Balaton Sound, Sziget Festival). An average of 8-10 replies also arrived in connection with tablets, game software, car parts or a wellness weekend. There were fewer votes on pets and beauticians (hairdresser, artificial nails, makeup, and solarium) and sports. Interestingly, useful objects were also longed for such as books for school, equipment and nearly 40 would take this sum to a bank or invest it, e.g. on the stock exchange. Two would go on studying, 12 would give it to the parents (to pay the bills, mortgage, a fridge or logs) and 25 would buy a present for their loved ones or the needy. Eight would opt for gambling and all concretely mentioned Tipp-mix. Most lists would be more expensive than the amount fixed as there were some listing items worth millions. This reflects the importance of money and sometimes the teenagers do not know the prices of the objects, either.

Table 2. The most severe environmental problems

Factor	Number of cases	Factor	Number of cases
environmental pollution in general	27	people's negligence, carelessness	7
water pollution (rivers, lakes, oceans) • from which oil spills: 11	55	manufacturing too many products (food, objects), wasting, overproduction	12
soil contamination	6	extreme weather	3
air pollution • from which smog: 18 • atmosphere: 2 • factory smoke: 51 • noxious gases: 2 • exhaust fumes of cars, buses: 35 • CO2 emission: 8	163	greenhouse effect	4
littering • from which electronic waste: 1 • illegal dumpsites (forests, near roads): 7	117	cigarette fags	4
deforestation	24	smoking	7
depletion and overusing of resources	11	UV radiation	3
wasting water	6	ozone hole, ozone layer	10
killing animal species	9	incineration	4
poisonous agents and chemical materials in the environment	15	atomic power plans, nuclear energy	4
global warming	17	CFC (sprays)	2
Others /(mentioned once) • soil erosion • melting of ice caps • bomb experiments • cows • earthquake • poisonous food and medicine • modernization • Diesel cars • space litter			

Source: authors compilation

The final question of the topic was how the students see their own future and how the Earth would look like in 40-45 years when they are 60. Different factors from the list had to be evaluated whether they think it is probable or not. They did not see the destruction of animals and plants or biological diversity as an acute problem and also they were very uncertain about wars, international conflicts and terrorism. Orwellian future was not an option for them saying it is fiction. Similarly, air pollution and its impacts as well as rising sea levels were not regarded serious, either or as a factor that would greatly influence the future. Further remarks reflect that the problem of littering is important as it was already proved in listing environmental problems. Maybe the most concrete problem in their lives is what they can see with their own eyes and believe. The last statement had an interesting result as overpopulation is a very common topic nowadays saying that we have exceeded 7 billion on Earth, we deplete our resources etc. but more than we thought said the population of the Earth would decrease.

Knowledge was tested by the rapid questions of the second questionnaire. Of the three possible alternatives the good one had to be marked. Unfortunately, the results imply asking for help from outside so they are useful to see the trend but exact statistics are not available. We could see the highest ratio of good answers in years 11 and 12 proving that the more mature they get, the more knowledge they have on the components of sustainability will also become clearer. The questions were diverse ranging from paleolite diet to the Red Book, fair trade and indigenous species. In general, there were more good answers and, of course, uncertainty could also be seen at some points. Unfortunately, most students believed heck is a fish in Lake Balaton, monoculture an African tribe, chlorophyll as a cleanser but most of them also knew why it is forbidden to touch stalactites, what pollutes the water most or what should be done with snowdrops. However, the nature and diversity of the questions gave a quite clear picture about the quality of the knowledge of the generation on sciences and sustainability.

Conclusions

Examining the sustainability of tourism is quite a complex task, which was approached from the part of the tourist of the future in this case. To protect the destination, the socio-economic features and behaviour of the tourists is decisive (David et. al. 2012). This can be influenced to a certain extent while travelling, preparing or on the spot but the question what information the tourist has on sustainability in general and what they are willing to do for it is more decisive. Typically, ethical travellers only extent their everyday behaviour while travelling and no special efforts are

made. All this would take us back to education. The present paper tries to highlight it in the case of the students of a concrete school, i.e. Istvan Szechenyi Roman Catholic Secondary school in Hatvan. The results help highlight the points of interference and give us an exact picture about how the next generations should be treated by the decision makers in the future and cooperate with them so that tourism could entirely be sustainable.

Transportation in the examined group showed a mixed picture as public transportation was assessed positively. This gives us hope if they grow to like it when young, then later they are more willing to choose this alternative which is more sustainable and less harmful to the environment than the car. However, the results are discouraging in connection with using bicycles. One hundred and sixty-eight (64%) students live within 5 km from school, which could be covered in a few minutes as the area is a plain. The school has a facility for storing bikes but regarding the number of cyclist path, the city still has a lot to do. Improving them can make statistics much better but it would be essential to call the attention of the students to the importance of doing exercises and the advantages of cycling. It is a crucial issue for their health and the cleanliness of the environment as well as shaping their lifestyle in the future, where apparently not enough attention is paid by the education.

Teaching the importance of selective waste collection at this age would also be decisive. Unfortunately, it would not be a custom and part of everyday life till the students realise it is not a fag, rather a step taken for the environment. Selective collection at schools and a lot of information on it could help a lot. The problem of waste is caused by not enough knowledge, too, as students cannot be encouraged till they know what damage plenty of waste can do to the environment and they will not realise their responsibility in this system, either.

In our constantly changing, rapid world food and dishes have different interpretations than for the previous generations. The new trends, the different diets and fags, the intensive marketing of fast food chains have an impact on the teenagers, which is also a social problem as the ratio of overweight children and adults is very high in Hungary. In this case sustainability is linked to health consciousness, and it is very difficult and may not be sensible to separate them. Unfortunately, the eating habits of the Hungarian teenagers do not move towards health and even if this is an acute problem, changes still need time. Good examples and reforming canteens must be widely spread and the food and drink supplies at schools should strictly be regulated. Improving the situation of the local produce and producers and offering home-made and traditional flavours and healthy food at

schools could help students realise valuable nutrients in the future, respect regional specialities and be conscious travellers. In this concrete case, the drastic transformation of the buffet's supplies could be necessary and also more information could be given on the dangers of obesity, the distribution of food and its ingredients.

Nowadays education has a lot of challenges as information technology totally changed almost everything. Students can easily get information, study materials and tests from the internet so traditional teaching methods and techniques must be changed. The religious background of the institution in Hatvan could serve as a very good basis for an education that emphasises sustainability on ethical basics as the concept of an eco-school is in the short-term plans.

The respondents were aware of most forms of environmental pollution and global problems but the solutions were entirely unknown for them. Education can play the most decisive role here as the students have nothing to do with cutting the rainforest along the Amazon because it is a distant and unknown area for them and it cannot be linked to their everyday life. It would be more important to explain what their role is in the system and where they could also do something. Such priority could be consumption, shopping and everyday objects. The sample possessed several things and they would require more so their consumption structure cannot be maintained. It should be time to rationalise and manage it and also explain the consequences.

Summary

Making tourism sustainable is a very hard way of the most positive scenarios for the future. However, a great number of local initiatives and the programmes of national and global organisations, the medium-and long-term tourism development directions and strategies prove that this could be the way to the sensible maintenance of this industry. Travelling is becoming part of more and more people every day and there are more and more players of this global mobility. Coordinating it is not possible but best practices and efforts to minimise harmful effects can be effective in the long term. The new generations who enter national and international tourism can also have a great impact on it. Regarding the fact that the industry is being transformed, the role of information and technology is becoming greater and the expectations for the tourists are totally different from what it was like a few years ago.

The presently active generation, who experienced and lived through the changes can see the directions and know the possible consequences, must see communicating it to the next generation as their own task. The role of education is becoming more intense

and shifting to a direction where defining the right way and ethical behaviour also counts in addition to imparting enormous knowledge. Of course, it is a great responsibility on the shoulders of the teachers and the parents, a new situation for which there are no patterns to be followed in history but the potentials behind the gravity of this task must also be realised. There may be a chance to ease global problems and create a more liveable future and environment for the tourists of the future and their children, as it is one of the principles of sustainability.

The present study analyses this question from the side of the students by highlighting the way an average Hungarian secondary school takes in 2014 to sustainability and what points have to be changed where education and teachers can have a greater role. While analysing data it became obvious that the generation have enough knowledge on certain issues such as waste treatment and a healthy way of life but this knowledge is rather superficial. There are huge gaps in connection with the more serious connections, the connecting points of the systems and the technical implementation of the solution. The generation is open-minded and receptive so the task is obvious: to arouse their interest in the environment with best practices and examples to help them become travellers and adults who behave responsibly and ethically.

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